

ANÁLISE FITOQUÍMICA E AVALIAÇÃO DO EFEITO FITOTÓXICO DA FRAÇÃO HEXÂNICA DAS FOLHAS DE *Smilax brasiliensis* (SMILACACEAE)PHYTOCHEMICAL ANALYSIS AND EVALUATION OF THE PHYTOTOXIC EFFECT OF THE HEXANE FRACTION FROM THE LEAVES OF *Smilax brasiliensis* (SMILACACEAE)FONSECA, Juliana Costa¹; AMADO, Paula Avelar¹; CASTRO, Ana Hortência Fonsêca¹; LIMA, Luciana Alves Rodrigues dos Santos^{1*}¹Campus Centro-Oeste Dona Lindu, Universidade Federal de São João Del Rei

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RESUMO

As espécies do gênero *Smilax* são conhecidas como *salsaparrilha* ou *japecanga*, sendo muito usadas na medicina popular para o tratamento do reumatismo, sífilis, artrite, doenças da pele, e como tônico, anti-hipertensivo e diurético. Dessa forma, o objetivo deste estudo foi avaliar a atividade fitotóxica e identificar as principais classes de metabólitos secundários presentes na fração hexânica obtida das folhas de *Smilax brasiliensis*. As folhas foram coletadas, secas, trituradas e submetidas à extração por percolação com etanol, obtendo-se o extrato etanólico. Parte desse extrato foi particionado com hexano, resultando na fração hexânica. Os melhores resultados obtidos na avaliação da fitotoxicidade foram para as subfrações HEX4 e HEX5, na concentração de 250 µg por placa, para as sementes de *Lactuca sativa*. Ao avaliar a fitotoxicidade para as sementes de *Allium cepa*, os melhores resultados foram da subfração HEX1 para a radícula e da subfração HEX2 para o hipocótilo, ambas na concentração de 125 µg por placa. A análise fitoquímica revelou a presença de cumarinas, esteroides e flavonoides na fração hexânica, sugerindo que a atividade fitotóxica possa ser atribuída, ao menos parcialmente a esses compostos; entretanto, estudos adicionais são necessários. Estes resultados sugerem que futuramente a fração hexânica das folhas de *S. brasiliensis* possa ser usada como herbicida natural.

Palavras-chave: Salsaparrilha, *Smilax brasiliensis*, análise fitoquímica, fitotóxico.

ABSTRACT

The species of *Smilax* genus are known as *sarsaparilla* or *japecanga*, being widely used in folk medicine as a tonic, antirheumatic, anti-syphilitic, antihypertensive and diuretic and for sweating, arthritis and skin conditions. Thus, the aim of this study was to evaluate the phytotoxic activity and to identify the main classes of secondary metabolites present in the hexane fraction obtained from *Smilax brasiliensis*. The leaves were collected, dried, crushed and extracted by percolation with ethanol, obtaining the ethanol extract. Part of this extract was partitioned with hexane, resulting in the hexane (HEX) fraction. The best results by the phytotoxic activity in *Lactuca sativa* seeds were for the HEX4 and HEX5 sub-fractions, at concentration of 250 µg per plate. When evaluating the phytotoxicity in *Allium cepa* seeds, the best results were found for the HEX1 sub-fraction for the radicle and the HEX2 sub-fraction for the hypocotyl, both at concentration of 125 µg per plate. Phytochemical analysis revealed the presence of coumarins, steroids and flavonoids in the hexane fraction, suggesting that the phytotoxic activity may be attributed at least partially to these compounds; however, additional studies are needed. These results suggest that in the future, the hexane fraction of *S. brasiliensis* leaves can be used as a natural herbicide.

Keywords: Sarsaparilla, *Smilax brasiliensis*, phytochemical analysis, phytotoxic.

1. INTRODUCTION

The growth of the world population implies in the increase of food production, and in addition, there is also a greater use of herbicides for the control of weeds in the crops. Although this method of chemical control is practical and efficient, it has several limitations. The use of synthetic herbicides sometimes leads to environmental pollution, in addition to causing other effects, such as resistance (Duke *et al.*, 2000; Hachinohe and Matsumoto, 2007).

The plants have, in their constitution, several compounds with allelopathic action called allelochemicals (Delmondes *et al.*, 2013). These compounds are secondary metabolites belonging to various classes such as terpenes, alkaloids, phenolic compounds, steroids, long chain fatty acids and unsaturated lactones (Malheiros and Peres, 2001). In recent years, several efforts have been made to identify natural allelochemicals with phytotoxic properties that offer new and excellent opportunities to diversify weed control in Brazilian agriculture and in other countries (Souza Filho *et al.*, 2005).

In this context, the *Smilax* genus may be an alternative source of natural herbicides. Triterpenoids, flavonoids, steroidal saponins, phenolic acids and phytosterols are the main components found in species this genus (Breitbach *et al.*, 2013; Cáceres *et al.*, 2012; Wu *et al.*, 2014).

Smilax brasiliensis Sprengel is a monocotyledon, belonging to the family Smilacaceae, popularly known as *sarsaparilla* or *japecanga*. The species is found in the Brazilian Cerrado, widely distributed in the Midwest and Southeast regions (Andreata, 2014), and used in folk medicine for rheumatism, as anti-syphilitic and capillary tonic (Guarim Neto and Morais, 2003; Martins *et al.*, 2013), therapeutic agent in immunoinflammatory diseases, such as rheumatoid arthritis (Jiang and Xu, 2003).

Due to the scarce studies related for *S. brasiliensis*, the aim of this work was to evaluate the phytotoxic activity and presence of the main classes of secondary metabolites in the leaves of this species.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Chemicals

For this study, 2- (*N*-morpholino)

ethanesulfonic acid (MES) purchased from Sigma-Aldrich® (USA) was used. Sulfuric acid, hexane, ethanol, ferric chloride, sodium hydroxide, ethyl acetate, toluene and acetic anhydride purchased from Cromato Produtos Químicos® (Brazil). The reagents basic bismuth nitrate, potassium iodide and acetic acid were obtained from Vetec® (Brazil).

2.2. Plant material and extraction

Smilax brasiliensis Sprengel (Smilacaceae) leaves were collected in the Cerrado region of Ijaci, South Minas Gerais State, Brazil (21°13'46" S and 44°55'65" W, average altitude 908 m) in March 2014 (SISBIO n. 24542-5). Fertile samples were collected, and vouchers were identified by Dr. Regina Helena Potsch Andreata, and deposited in the PAMG Herbarium (PAMG 57078) at the Agricultural Research Company of Minas Gerais (EPAMIG). This work has access permission to the components of plant genetic heritage (n. 010455/2014-0/CNPq/CGEN/MMA).

Extraction of the dried and powdered leaves (115.13 g) by percolation (ethanol, 7 L, 72 h) produced ethanol extract (EE) (23.40 g). Part of this extract (15.60 g) was dissolved in ethanol/water (1:1) and successively extracted with hexane, dichloromethane and ethyl acetate, resulting in 4.76, 2.68, 1.65 and 5.72 g of hexane (HEX), dichloromethane (DCM), ethyl acetate (AC) and hydroethanol (HE) fractions, respectively (Fonseca *et al.*, 2017).

2.3. Phytochemical analysis

Phytochemical screening of the hexane fraction was performed to evaluate the presence of the main classes of secondary metabolites: flavonoids, saponins, tannins, coumarins, alkaloids, steroids and triterpenoids (Silva *et al.*, 2010; Matos, 2009), characterized by chemical reactions that result in the development of staining, precipitation and foams.

2.4. Phytotoxic activity test by bioautography

Phytotoxicity tests were done using only the hexane fraction that strongly inhibits *Allium cepa* seed germination in Petri dishes (Fonseca *et al.* 2017). Chromatography plates [silica gel matrix (5.5 x 5.5 cm)] with fluorescent indicator staining (Sigma Aldrich) and hexane fraction were eluted into the chromatography chamber

using toluene/ethyl acetate 93:7 (eluted twice), and then placed into Petri dishes (10.0 Ø). A piece of filter paper was placed over the fraction-containing chromatography plates and seeds were placed on top, as per thin-layer chromatography (TLC) profiles visualized under UV light and previously highlighted in the fraction-containing chromatography plates; 10 mL of MES buffer (pH 6.0) was then added. *Lactuca sativa* L. var. cabbage (lettuce) (Feltrin®, Lot 0132090100, Brazil) and *Allium cepa* cv. Baia Periforme (onion) (Feltrin®, Lot 0003801411000010, Brazil) were added to the Petri dishes; 25 seeds were added per plate. To make the control, the same amount of buffer was added to a Petri dish containing a blank chromatography plate and the same amount of seeds.

After a week of incubation in the dark, the Petri dishes were frozen at -10 °C for 24 h to stop plant growth. The size of hypocotyls and radicles of germinated *A. cepa* and *L. sativa* seeds were measured as a function of the chromatographic profile (Tonelli *et al.*, 2014). The effects on growth were calculated using the following formula (Pinto *et al.*, 2013):

$$\% \text{ of growth} = \frac{Ma - Mc}{Mc} \times 100 \text{ (Eq. 1)}$$

where Ma is the mean value of the seeds with test samples and Mc is the mean value for the control (seeds grown without the addition of test samples). Thus, zero represents the control, positive values represent stimulation of growth and negative values represent inhibition of growth.

2.5. Statistical analysis

A Student's t-test was used to evaluate the statistical difference between the control group and the group exposed to hexane fraction of *S. brasiliensis*. The analyses were performed using GraphPad Prism 5.0 software (San Diego, CA, USA). Values were considered statistically significant at $p < 0.05$.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Phytochemical tests revealed the presence of coumarins, flavonoids and steroids in hexane fraction (Table 1). Coumarins, flavonoids and saponins has already detected in *S. campestris* (Morais *et al.*, 2014). Flavonoids,

saponins, coumarins and tannins were found in the extract and fractions of *S. domingensis* rhizomes (Cáceres *et al.*, 2012).

The chromatographic profile of hexane fraction by TLC plate exhibited five spots with different Rf: HEX1 (Rf 0.0), which corresponds to the beginning of the chromatographic run, HEX2 (Rf 0.27), HEX3 (Rf 0.36). Between the Rfs 0.36 and 1.0, the intermediate profile (HEX4) is found, a portion apparently free of substances and, then, at the end of the chromatographic run, the HEX5 (Rf 1.0). The phytotoxic effects of the hexane fraction from *S. brasiliensis* leaves on *L. sativa* and *A. cepa* radicles and hypocotyls were evaluated at three different concentrations; results are shown in Figures 1 and 2.

The hexane fraction presented strongly phytotoxic effects on the radicle and hypocotyl of *L. sativa*, inhibiting 100% of growth in all Rfs, at concentration of 500 µg per plate, and in HEX4 and HEX5 sub-fractions, at concentration of 250 µg per plate (Figure 1A and 1B).

The growth of the *A. cepa* radicles and hypocotyls are shown in Figure 2. The HEX sub-fractions showed stimulatory and inhibitory effects on hypocotyl and radicle growth. The strongest inhibitory effects were observed with HEX1 (65.09%), at concentration of 125 µg per plate, and HEX1 (52.15%) and HEX2 (52.87%), at concentration of 500 µg per plate, on radicle growth (Figure 2A). As for hypocotyl growth, the best results were the inhibition of 55.58% (HEX2) and 48.10% (HEX1), at concentration of 125 µg per plate, and 51.30% (HEX1), at 500 µg per plate (Figure 2B).

As such, results suggest that the HEX fraction presented phytotoxic potential and showed the strongest effects with HEX4 and HEX5 for *L. sativa*, at concentration of 250 µg per plate, and HEX1 for the radicle and HEX2 for the hypocotyl of *A. cepa*, at a concentration of 125 µg per plate. In the phytotoxic assay, the HEX sub-fractions were statistically significant when compared to the control ($p < 0.05$).

The inhibition of radicle and hypocotyl growth on lettuce and onion seeds when exposed to hexane fraction is related to the secondary metabolites present in this species. Phenolic derivatives, such as flavonoids and coumarins, have ability to interfere with plant development (Soares *et al.*, 2002), affecting processes related to plant growth and development, and can be used to increase or reduce agricultural productivity (Xuan *et al.*, 2005). Coumarins are indicated as potent inhibitors of plant growth and seed germination, possessing the ability to block

mitosis (Abenavoli *et al.*, 2006; Rice, 1984; Willis, 2007). Studies involving allelopathic activity of steroids are not frequent in the literature; however, these compounds are associated with the reduction of radicle and hypocotyl development, evidencing allelopathic effect (Inoue *et al.*, 2010).

To the best of our knowledge, reports about the phytotoxic potential of the *Smilax* genus are scarce. Phytotoxicity activity of *S. medica* species was done on *Zea mays* seeds exhibiting maximum inhibitory activity in root growth (Khan *et al.*, 2016). Barbosa *et al.* (2019) demonstrated the phytotoxic potential of dichloromethane (DCM) sub-fractions from *S. brasiliensis* leaves, at concentration of 125 µg per plate, with best results for DCM6 and DCM4 on *L. sativa* and *A. cepa* seeds, respectively.

There are few reports about the allelopathic activity of *S. brasiliensis*. Fonseca *et al.* (2017) evaluated the allelopathic potential of ethanol extract and fractions of *S. brasiliensis* leaves on *A. cepa* and *L. sativa* radicles and hypocotyls, with strongly inhibitory activity on the growth of *A. cepa* hypocotyls and radicles. Amado *et al.* (2019) also showed the allelopathic effects of extracts, fatty acids and methyl esters (FAMES) from leaves, which inhibited the growth of *A. cepa* roots and shoots; however, a diversified response was obtained on *L. sativa* seeds, with inhibition or promotion seeds growth.

4. CONCLUSIONS

In summary, the best results by the phytotoxic activity in *L. sativa* seeds were for the HEX4 and HEX5, at concentration of 250 µg per plate. When evaluating the phytotoxicity in *A. cepa* seeds, the best results were found for the HEX1 in radicle and the HEX2 in hypocotyl, both at concentration of 125 µg per plate. Thus, these results encourage the deepening of the studies with *S. brasiliensis* species, making it possible to use them as natural herbicide, with a lower harmful effect on the environment.

5. ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

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Figure 1. Phytotoxic effects of the hexane fraction (HEX) (μg per plate) from *Smilax brasiliensis* leaves on the radicle (A) and hypocotyl (B) growth of *Lactuca sativa*.

Figure 2. Phytotoxic effects of the hexane fraction (HEX) (μg per plate) from *Smilax brasiliensis* leaves on the radicle (A) and hypocotyl (B) growth of *Allium cepa*.

Table 1. Results of phytochemical analysis.

Secondary Metabolites	HEX
Alkaloids	-
Anthraquinones	-
Coumarins	+
Steroids	+
Triterpenes	-
Flavonoids	+
Saponins	-
Tannins	-

HEX: hexane fraction, Positive: +, Negative: -.